

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

STIFFENED COMPOSITE PARTS BY RESIN INFUSION PROCESS FOR AIRCRAFT APPLICATION

KOLON DACC COMPOSITE, R&D Centre

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CONFERENCE
HOSTS:

CONFERENCE
DESTINATION
SUPPORTERS:

#ICCM22

KOLON DACC COMPOSITE

Established Nov. 2001

Incorporated into KOLON Group in Dec. 2015

Business Area : Advanced Composite

Location: 26-23, Hamansandan 1Gil, Gyeongnam, S. KOREA

- 2018 Established the Ballistic Laboratory
- 2015 Incorporated into KOLON Group.
- 2013 Contracted Composite Structure for Submarine
- 2012 Contracted Korea GPS Guide Bomb KIT
- 2012 Export T-50 External Fuel Tank(Indonesia, etc.)
- 2009 Contracted Korea VLS
- 2008 Contracted Infantry Fighting Vehicle Armor
- 2007 Certified AS9100, BSI
- 2006 Certified Defense Quality System (DTaQ)
- 2002 Designated as a Member : Korea Defense Industry
- 2001 Established(Spin off from KAI Ltd.)

Aerospace	Defense	Automobile
AS9100 Rev. D	GE (Composites Bonding)	NADCAP AC7118 (Composite Bonding)
	KDS 0050-9000-3	IATF 16949

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Project Outline

Low Cost Carbon Composite

With Low Cost Materials

With Low Cost Manufacturing

With High Quality

Manufacturing	<p>Low MH Low cost installation High rate with high quality</p>	→ Resin Infusion
Materials	<p>Easy to maintain Low cost</p>	→ Carbon NCF with epoxy
Design	<p>Easy to fabricate Structural stability Light Weight</p>	→ Composite Design

Structural Design & Analysis

AI Designed MLG Door

Failure Mode: 1st Ply Failure
 Load Case: Opening Load
 MS: +0.01

Failure Mode: 1st Ply Failure
 Load Case: Opening Load
 MS: +0.20

535EA Fasteners
in metal structure

92EA Fasteners
in Composite structure

Material

Carbon Non Clamped Fabric (NCF)

a Carbon Finer Tow (12k, 5mm) **b** Spreading Carbon Fiber (12k, 25mm)

Resin & Resin Film

Manufacturing

Product Results

